

IMPACT OF PLANT-FUNGI SYMBIOSIS ON PHOTOSYNTHESIS AND NUTRITION**Shirin Mahmudova***Ph.D., Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University***Gultakin Arabova***Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University***Abstract**

The interactions between plants and fungi play a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem balance and plant health. Fungi interact with plants in three main ways: symbiosis (mutually beneficial), parasitism (harmful), and saprotrophy (breaking down dead organic matter to enrich the soil). Mycorrhizal fungi enhance plant nutrient and water uptake, boosting photosynthesis and increasing resistance to drought and saline soils. However, pathogenic fungi disrupt nutrient balance, alter hormonal regulation, and weaken photosynthesis. Beneficial fungi protect plants from harmful microorganisms and promote growth. The impact of fungi on plants depends on environmental conditions and specific plant-fungi relationships.

Keywords: Carbohydrate balance, water and mineral nutrient uptake, plant-fungi interactions, mycorrhizal fungi, phytopathogenic fungi, plant defense mechanisms, symbiotic relationships.

As much as we encounter a variety of living things in the world, each ecosystem they create maintains the balance of all life with its own unique features. Plants occupy an important place among the living things that produce the main oxygen in nature and form the basis of the food chain. Their growth and development are shaped under the influence of various ecological and biotic factors. Among these factors, fungi are of particular importance. All living things in these ecosystems live in harmony with each other. The relationships between plants and fungi play a crucial role in the balance of ecosystems and plant health. These relationships have been formed over millions of years of evolution and have helped plants grow, feed, and adapt to their environment more efficiently (Smith & Read, 2008). Fungi interact with plants in various ways. Some fungi form beneficial symbiotic relationships, while others are parasitic and cause serious damage to plants. A full understanding of these relationships is always relevant to open up new opportunities for agriculture and ecological balance management in the face of anthropogenic impacts, rapidly changing environments, and ecological problems.

Interactions between plants and fungi are mainly divided into three categories. Symbiotic relationships are mutually beneficial relationships between fungi and plants, for example, mycorrhizal fungi help to obtain water and minerals from the soil, and in return obtain carbohydrates from the plant. Some fungi enter the tissues of plants and feed by parasitizing them, slowing their development and causing various diseases. Fungi, which improve the nutrient composition of the soil by breaking down dead organisms, are saprotrophic. These relationships have an impact on the physiological processes occurring in the plant and fungal organisms. The effect of fungi on plants directly affects their photosynthetic activity, water and nutrient uptake, and resistance to environmental stress factors. The article will review the effects of plant-fungus relationships on photosynthesis and nutrition, both positive and negative aspects.

Mycorrhizal fungi live with the roots of plants, facilitating the absorption of nutrients. In turn, the

plants provide the fungi with the carbohydrates they need. Mycorrhizal fungi help plant roots absorb more water and minerals (phosphorus, nitrogen, potassium, etc.) from the soil (Smith & Read, 2008). This ensures that plants have access to more raw materials for photosynthesis and increases the photosynthetic activity of plants at the leaf level (Bonfante & Genre, 2010). The nutrients taken in by the fungi cause the chloroplasts to function more efficiently. The sugars synthesized as a result of photosynthesis are shared with the fungi, regulating the carbohydrate cycle. The fungi, in turn, use these sugars in their own metabolic processes, strengthening the symbiotic relationship (van der Heijden et al., 2015). Plants that interact with fungi become more resistant to drought, salty soils, and other environmental stressors. This allows the photosynthesis process to remain stable and the plants to grow healthier. Mycorrhizal fungi form a symbiotic relationship with plant roots, helping them absorb water and minerals from a wider area in the soil. Fungi also help plants maintain osmotic balance. They prevent water loss and reduce dehydration by regulating osmotic pressure within the cell (Moore et al., 2011). This is especially important in drought and saline soils, as plants can access limited resources more efficiently (Smith & Read, 2008). *However, this situation varies depending on the nature of the fungi. Phytopathogens secrete zinc-mobilizing enzymes (invertase, polygalacturonase) that alter the distribution of sugars and other organic substances. This leads to the transfer of photosynthesis products to the infection site and the weakening of plant growth processes.* For example, while the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungus *Rhizophagus irregularis* has a positive effect on the metabolism of corn (*Zae maydis*) plants, the fungus *Ustilago maydis* enters the tissues of corn and changes its carbohydrate balance. The sugars produced as a result of photosynthesis are absorbed by the fungus, reducing the plant's energy source. At the same time, it disrupts the hormonal balance in the plant and causes abnormal swellings.

The symbiotic relationship between wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), *Pisolithus tinctorius* ectomycorrhizal fungi and pine

trees (*Pinus spp.*) in addition to absorbing water and minerals, also plays a role in regulating carbohydrate balance. *Botrytis cinerea* is a necrotrophic phytopathogen that kills plant cells in grapes (*Vitis vinifera*), tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*), strawberries (*Fragaria × ananassa*), etc. and releases sugars. Abnormal changes in sugar concentration weaken the plant's own defense mechanism. Since the plant cannot regulate its sugar balance, it becomes more sensitive and begins to decay rapidly. *Magnaporthe oryzae* in rice, *Puccinia spp.* in cereals, and *Fusarium oxysporum* in vegetable plants damage xylem and phloem tubes and tissues, disrupting the course of metabolic processes and causing damage to plants.

Fungi increase the production of hormones such as abscisic acid and jasmonate in response to stress in plants. These hormones help regulate stomata and reduce the plant's water loss. (van der Heijden et al., 2015). *Rhizophagus irregularis* forms a symbiotic relationship with the roots of tomato plants, increasing the synthesis of abscisic acid. This hormone partially closes the stomata, reducing water evaporation and increasing the plant's resistance to drought. Mycorrhizal fungi also increase the production of the hormone jasmonate, which strengthens the plant's defense system. The same result can be observed in the symbiosis of *Epichloë festucae* with meadow grasses, and *Laccaria bicolor* with pine and oak trees. Phytopathogenic fungi, on the other hand, inhibit plant growth and development by blocking auxin synthesis. For example, toxins secreted by *Gibberella fujikuroi* can cause abnormal plant growth or stunting. Although salicylic acid and jasmonate lipid-based phytohormones enhance the defense mechanism against the pathogen, they can weaken photosynthesis and growth. For example, in plants infected with *Botrytis cinerea*, although increasing jasmonate levels increases defense, they slow down growth and disrupt the course of photosynthesis. Thus, increasing salicylic acid and jasmonate levels can cause stomata to close. Although stomata closure increases the plant's resistance to drought and pathogens, it limits the entry of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the leaves. As a result of the lack of CO₂, the main raw material for photosynthesis, carbon fixation decreases and photosynthetic activity weakens (Ding et al., 2018). Salicylic acid and jasmonate activate defense reactions within the cell and also increase the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). High levels of ROS accumulation damage chloroplasts, cause chlorophyll breakdown, and disrupt the electron transport chain (Gupta et al., 2020). This leads to a decrease in the efficiency of photosynthesis.

Fungi also participate in the fight against harmful microorganisms. For example, fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* protect plant roots from harmful bacteria. Fungi such as *Trichoderma* make plants more resistant to biotic and abiotic stresses. They protect plant cells from harmful effects by activating antioxidant defense mechanisms. Beneficial fungi stimulate the production of plant hormones such as auxin and cytokinin, which accelerate the growth of roots and shoots. Saprophytic fungi improve the structure of the soil by breaking

down cellulose and lignin, decompose dead plant and animal remains, enrich the soil with nutrients that can be absorbed by plants, and support the natural soil cycle. These mechanisms give plants advantages in surviving extreme conditions and ensure the continuity of their photosynthetic activity.

Although some fungi are in a symbiotic relationship with plants, under certain conditions they can negatively affect their physiology by secreting toxins and harmful metabolites. They can negatively affect the physiology of plants by producing toxins or harmful metabolites. Although these fungi sometimes benefit plants in the initial stage, under certain conditions they secrete substances - mycotoxins - that negatively affect their development and productivity. *Epichloë species* (*Epichloë* and *Neotyphodium*) increase the tolerance of cereal plants (ryegrass) to stress and herbivores, but produce toxins such as ergot alkaloids, causing poisoning for animals that feed on the grass (Schardl et al., 2013). In animals, it causes neurological disorders, vasoconstriction, and fertility problems. *Fusarium spp.* can, under certain conditions, stimulate growth by contacting plant roots in wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), corn (*Zea mays*), and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), but they can produce mycotoxins (e.g., zearalenone, fumonisin, and deoxynivalenol). These mycotoxins reduce the quality of grain products and are dangerous to humans. (Munkvold, 2017). *Alternaria alternata* can live as a symbiont in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) plants, but under stress conditions it secretes toxins (alternariotoxins) that can impair photosynthesis and damage cell membranes (Thomma, 2003). It causes necrosis in fruits and leaves, reducing yield. Although *Colletotrichum spp.* acts as a symbiont in legumes under certain conditions, it can become a hemibiotrophic parasite under stress factors and cause anthracnose disease (O'Connell et al., 2012). *Claviceps purpurea* (Ergot fungus) grows in the flowers of rye, wheat, and barley and can affect tissues by secreting ergot alkaloids. These toxins cause serious health problems in humans and animals. (Gang et al., 2015).

Some types of symbiosis, such as some mycorrhizal fungi, can weaken the plant by ceasing to be beneficial under unfavorable conditions (Moore et al., 2011). The transition of fungi to parasitism, that is, initially having a beneficial symbiotic relationship and later becoming harmful to the plant, can occur under the influence of various ecological and physiological factors. The main factors include the chemical composition of the soil, nutrient balance, water shortage and the physiological state of the plant. If soil conditions are unfavorable for the fungus (for example, when there is little water or nutrients), the fungus can damage it by sucking more nutrients from the plant. Although mycorrhizal fungi provide water and nutrients to plants under normal conditions, under unfavorable conditions (for example, when there is excess phosphorus and nitrogen in the soil) they can increase the plant's demand for carbohydrates. Also, under stress conditions (drought, saline soil, nutrient deficiency), the fungus may provide less benefit to the

plant and may even be a burden to it. For these reasons, a transition to parasitism is observed in fungi.

Plant-fungal relationships play an important role in maintaining the stability of the ecological system. Mycorrhizal fungi increase plant growth and soil fertility, while parasitic fungi damage plants by spreading diseases. However, in some cases, symbiotic fungi can have a negative effect on plants. Beneficial plant-fungal relationships play an important role in natural ecosystems and agriculture, as they regulate nutrient cycling and increase the resistance of plants to environmental stresses. A better understanding of this process is essential for optimizing the use of mycorrhiza in agriculture. The study of phytopathogenic fungi is important to consider the risks posed by these fungi in agriculture and to apply appropriate control measures. A complete understanding of symbiotic relationships will open up new opportunities in agricultural and environmental management.

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